
WORKPLACE DEMOCRATIC PRACTICES AND WORKFORCE SUSTAINABILITY OF MANUFACTURING COMPANIES IN RIVES STATE

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the relationship between workplace democratic practices and the workforce sustainability of manufacturing companies in Rives State. The study adopted a cross-sectional research design. The population of the study consisted of 450 respondents in seven (7) manufacturing firms in Rivers State. A sample size of 212 participants was derived from the population using Taro Yamene's formula. A questionnaire was used in data collection, and the data were analyzed using structural equation modeling, which comprised the statistical tools necessary for the hypothesis testing. The result indicated a significant relationship between workplace democratic practices and the workforce sustainability of manufacturing companies in Rives State. Based on the findings, the study concludes that workplace democratic practices relate to the workforce sustainability of manufacturing companies in Rives State. Therefore, it is recommended that management promote diversity and inclusivity in the workplace in order to improve work-life balance in manufacturing companies in Rives State. They should provide diversity and inclusion training programs to enhance the work-life balance of manufacturing companies in Rhodes State. Management should establish effective communication channels to improve work-life balance and encourage regular and transparent communication between management and employees to improve the work-life balance of manufacturing companies in Rives State.

Keywords: Workplace Democratic Practices, employee participation, employee development, Workforce Sustainability, Employee well-being

Introduction

The concept of a sustainable workforce has gained popularity recently due to the workplace's intense focus on profits, which often comes at the expense of workers' welfare. A loving and supportive work environment that promotes employee wellness is a sustainable workplace or workforce. Workers are no longer seen as essentially resources that may be used (and exhausted) to further the financial objectives of employers. They do not exhaust or misuse their abilities, talents, or energy. They are not subjected to an excessive workload or a relentless work tempo for many weeks or years at a time. Employees are granted time off during crisis situations (natural catastrophes, illness, etc.) so they may heal or look for the additional resources they'll need to perform in the future. Employees are spared from burnout and given time to recover. A sustainable use of human resources enables individuals to prosper, be creative, and innovate in addition to meeting in-role or necessary job expectations.

Cooker and Fry (2012) claim that sustainable HRM practices encourage pleasant social connections at work, which enhance HRM cohesiveness, employee engagement in a common objective, optimism for success, resilience, knowledge sharing, and collaborative skills. As per Pfeffer (2010), scholars and researchers consider workforce sustainability to be the influence of organizational activities on individuals' physical and emotional health and overall well-being. The stress that work practices place on the human system, the impact of management practices such as work hours and behaviors that undermine group cohesion as well as the richness of social life as evidenced by participation in civic, volunteer, and community organizations Manufacturing businesses, however, seem to need to consider a few factors that appear to have an effect on workforce sustainability in spite of these benefits. Within the context of workplace democracy, Peterson and Spängs (2006) define workplace democracy as a variety of structural arrangements that link organizational decision-making to the interests and influence of employees at various levels. Employee development is included, as are industrial democracy, participatory management, and self-management (Crouch & Heller, 1983). It has components related to decision-making, equality, and participation.

The corpus of studies on workplace democracy reveals specific characteristics and outcomes (Deutsch, 1981; Rothschild, 1992; Butcher and Clarke, 2002) that have the capacity to transform individuals who work in organizations by elevating their social consciousness, public spirit, cooperation, political consciousness and engagement, and concern for the greater good (Dahl, 1985). Providing opportunities for skill development, training, mentoring, coaching, and feedback to enhance employees' capabilities and enable them to contribute effectively to the organization are examples of these characteristics, along with employee development (involving employees in decision-making processes, seeking their input and feedback, and valuing their contributions to the organization). In order to foster employee growth and learning, a culture that prioritizes fairness (i.e., transparent expectations, performance reviews, and equitable rules and processes for performance management, incentives, and recognition) as well as innovation, creativity, and learning from mistakes may be established (Noe, 2010). According to Greenberg (1990), being fair also entails handling complaints and disputes in an open and impartial way.

Although researchers have examined the relationship between workplace democratic practices and organisational performance, however, studies that examine the relationship between workplace democratic practices and workforce sustainability of manufacturing

companies in Rives State is still scare in literature. Therefore, to fill this gap, the present study examined three dimensions of workplace democratic practices (employee participation, employee development and fairness) in relation to workforce sustainability in terms of employee well-being.

Statement of the Problem

Manufacturing companies in Rivers State, Nigeria, face the challenge of effectively implementing workplace democratic practices while ensuring the long-term sustainability of their workforce. The problem faced by these firms encompasses a low level of work-life balance and a lack of provision for work-life balance, which led to disengagement, reduced motivation, and decreased job satisfaction among employees (Cohen, 1999). Manufacturing companies often operate in demanding and high-pressure environments, which can negatively impact the work-life balance of employees. The absence of policies and practices promoting work-life balance can lead to burnout, turnover, and difficulties in attracting and retaining skilled workers (Burke & Cooper, 2022). The manufacturing industry in Rivers State also faces challenges in providing adequate employee wellbeing. Employees may feel stagnant in their roles, leading to decreased motivation and higher turnover rates (Ogechukwu et al., 2020).

Addressing this problem is crucial for the manufacturing companies in Rivers State to improve workplace democratic practices in order to ensure the sustainability of their workforce. Viewing this situation as a critical problem facing these firms has required the present study to examine the relationship between workplace democratic practices and the workforce sustainability of manufacturing companies in Rives State in order to provide a solution to this problem.

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework of Workplace Democratic Practices and Workforce Sustainability of Manufacturing Firms in Rivers State for the purpose of this study.

Source: Research Desk as Variables Adapted from Cox (1994), Morgeson & Humphrey (2006), Noe (2010), Gallup (2021), Harter et al. (2002), and Hom et al., (2017).

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study is to examine the relationship between workplace democratic practices and workforce sustainability of manufacturing companies in Rives State. The objectives of the study are to:

- i. Investigate the relationship between employee participation and employee wellbeing of manufacturing companies in Rives State.
- ii. Evaluate the relationship between employee development and employee wellbeing of manufacturing companies in Rives State.
- iii. Ascertain the relationship between fairness and employee wellbeing of manufacturing companies in Rives State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were analyzed in the study:

1. What is the relationship between employee participation and employee wellbeing of manufacturing companies in Rives State?
2. How does employee development relate to employee wellbeing of manufacturing companies in Rives State?
3. What is the relationship between fairness and employee wellbeing of manufacturing companies in Rives State?

Research Hypotheses

The following statements of hypotheses were tested in the study:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between employee participation and employee wellbeing of manufacturing companies in Rives State.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between employee development and employee wellbeing of manufacturing companies in Rives State.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between fairness and employee wellbeing of manufacturing companies in Rives State.

Scope of the Study

The content scope of the study covers workplace democratic practices as independent variable with three of its dimensions such as employee participation, employee development and fairness. While, workforce sustainability is the dependent variable using work life balance as its measure for the purpose of this study.

The geographical scope of the study is the manufacturing firms in Rivers State.

The unit of analysis is the micro level because the study will examine the employees in the manufacturing firms.

Significance of the Study

The study on workplace democratic practices and workforce sustainability in manufacturing companies in Rivers State holds significant importance for various stakeholders, including manufacturing companies, employees, policymakers, and the overall economic development of the State. The significance of this study can be outlined as follows:

Manufacturing company performance: understanding the relationship between workplace democratic practices and workforce sustainability can provide manufacturing companies in rivers state with valuable insights into how these factors impact organizational performance by implementing democratic practices and promoting workforce sustainability, companies can enhance employee engagement, productivity, and overall business outcomes.

Employee Well-being and Job Satisfaction: The study's findings can shed light on the importance of workplace democratic practices and workforce sustainability in improving employee well-being and job satisfaction. By fostering a work environment that values employee participation, work-life balance, skill development, career advancement, and diversity, manufacturing companies can create a positive workplace culture that supports the overall well-being of their workforce.

Talent Attraction and Retention: Manufacturing companies in Rivers State can benefit from the study by understanding the factors that contribute to attracting and retaining top talent. In today's competitive labor market, companies that prioritize workplace democracy and workforce sustainability are more likely to attract skilled workers who seek an inclusive and engaging work environment.

Policy making: The study can inform policymakers and industry associations about the importance of promoting workplace democratic practices and workforce sustainability in the manufacturing sector. Policymakers can use the findings to develop supportive policies and regulations that encourage manufacturing companies to adopt democratic practices and sustainable workforce management strategies.

Economic Development: The manufacturing sector plays a vital role in the economic development of Rivers State. By promoting workplace democratic practices and workforce sustainability, manufacturing companies can contribute to the overall economic growth and stability of the state. Engaged and sustainable workforces drive innovation, productivity, and competitiveness, ultimately leading to a thriving manufacturing industry.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Theoretical Review

The study adopted two theories (Participative Decision-Making Theory and Spill-Over Theory) that support the concepts of workplace democratic practices and workforce sustainability. These theories were considered appropriate because participative decision-making theory tends to focus on workplace democratic practices while Spill-Over Theory place emphasis on the importance of workplace sustainability.

Participative Decision-Making Theory

The participatory decision-making theory is a well-known idea that serves as the foundation for democratic workplace practices. According to this theory, including workers in decision-

making procedures may result in better decisions, more dedication, and higher levels of job satisfaction. Cohen's (1999) study on participative decision-making provides insights into this theory. The study examines the effects of expertise, accountability, and pre-decisional information on decision quality and commitment. Cohen's research demonstrates that when employees are given the opportunity to participate in decision-making, particularly when they possess relevant expertise and have access to necessary information, decision quality and commitment to the decision are significantly higher. The theory of participative decision-making supports the idea that workplace democratic practices, such as involving employees in decision-making processes, can empower individuals, enhance their job satisfaction, and ultimately contribute to improved organizational performance. By considering diverse perspectives, knowledge, and experiences, participatory decision-making can lead to more effective and innovative solutions.

Spill-Over Theory (Staines, 1980)

According to this theory, professional life and family life are intertwined and have an impact on one another. In this manner, experiences and skills at work may influence experiences and abilities at home in both positive and negative ways, and vice versa. To explain the interaction between work and life as well as the many facets of the relationship between work/family enrichment, work/family conflict, and quality of life, as well as the reverse, this research uses Staines' (1980) Spillover Theory. The Spill-Over Theory can support work-life balance and workforce sustainability by recognizing that experiences and influences from one domain, such as work, can spill over into other domains, like personal life. This spill-over effect can have implications for individuals' well-being, satisfaction, and overall sustainability in both their personal and professional lives.

The Spill-Over Theory acknowledges that conflicts or stress experienced in the work domain can spill over into individuals' personal lives, potentially affecting their well-being and ability to balance work and personal responsibilities. For instance, high job demands or long working hours can lead to increased stress, fatigue, and decreased time and energy available for family, leisure activities, and self-care. Employers and individuals can utilize this understanding to promote strategies that mitigate negative spillover effects, such as implementing flexible work arrangements, promoting self-care initiatives, and fostering a supportive work environment.

The Spill-Over Theory can also contribute to workforce sustainability by recognizing the interplay between work and non-work domains. When individuals experience excessive negative spillover effects, such as chronic work-related stress or burnout, it can impact their overall well-being and job performance, potentially leading to reduced productivity, increased absenteeism, and higher turnover rates. Organizations that prioritize workforce sustainability can take steps to address spillover effects by implementing policies and practices that promote work-life balance, employee well-being, and effective stress management.

Conceptual Review

The conceptual review of this study covers the concept of workplace democratic practices in two dimensions, among others: diversity, inclusivity, and open communication. It also examined the concept of workforce sustainability with employee well-being as its measure, among others. These concepts are discussed below.

Concept of Workplace Democratic Practices

Workplace democracy practices include a range of values and conduct that encourage involvement, diversity, openness, and responsibility inside the organization. These procedures are intended to foster a democratic and cooperative workplace where workers are respected and treated with dignity, decision-making is shared, and employees have a voice. The concept of workplace democracy is complex, with origins in sociology, politics, economics, and labor history. Variations in the definitions of workplace democracy are caused by contextual considerations; nonetheless, common themes and concepts such as worker control, industrial democracy, organizational democracy, economic democracy, unionization, and work councils set them apart. Workplace democracy encompasses a range of institutional arrangements that link organizational decision-making to the interests and influence of employees at various levels (Petersson & Spängs, 2006). It encompasses decision-making, equality, and participation, and it goes from self-management and industrial democracy to employee engagement and participatory management (Crouch & Heller, 1983). Many concepts, such as industrial democracy, employee empowerment, employee engagement, and participatory management, have been claimed to be included in the concept of workplace democracy.

According to Peterson and Spängs (2006), workplace democracy refers to a range of structural mechanisms that link organizational decision-making to the influence and interests of workers at various levels. It includes ideas of participation, equality, and decision-making and spans from employee engagement and participatory management to industrial democracy and self-management (Crouch & Heller, 1983). Many concepts, such as industrial democracy, employee empowerment, employee engagement, and participatory management, have been claimed to be included in the concept of workplace democracy.

Levine and Tyson (1990) assert that enhanced business performance in areas like profit or gain sharing, job security, support for group cohesiveness, and individual rights is ensured when employees are supported in participating in decision-making. This result is consistent with the empirical study that Ben-Ner and Jones (1995) looked at, which showed that profit-sharing or gain-sharing programs only improve firm performance when they are used in tandem with participatory management systems, and vice versa. According to the study, organizations that provide financial incentives to groups also often use progressive management strategies that encourage worker involvement in firm- and shop-level planning and decision-making, further advancing "product and producer" alignment. Implementing workplace democracy as outlined in the literature (Deutsch, 1981; Rothschild, 1992; Butcher & Clarke, 2002) can make people in organizations more cooperative, socially conscious, cooperative, politically aware, and concerned for the greater good (Dahl, 1985).

From his study, Coutinho (2016) concluded that workplace democracy raises the bar for certain worker and employee groups, and that it has a detrimental effect on those people's well-being when that standard is not met. It should be mentioned that employees may abuse their right to dissent, revolt against the authority of management, and start a "virtual mutiny" (Kokemuller, 2017). Additional evidence for the unfavorable opinion of workplace democracy comes from the literature, which claims that although profit-sharing schemes are included in workplace democracy and improve efficiency, output, and performance, they also give room for the exploitation of "freeloaders (Freeloaders are individuals who habitually take advantage of others' generosity, resources, or efforts without reciprocating or

contributing themselves). It's important to establish boundaries and fair expectations when dealing with such behavior, ensuring that everyone involved contributes or benefits equitably.

Employee Participation

Democratic workplace practices are fundamentally based on employee involvement. It entails including staff members into decision-making procedures, asking for and appreciating their opinions and contributions to the company. This may be accomplished by using tools that let staff members voice their thoughts and views, such focus groups, town halls, questionnaires, and frequent team meetings (Morgeson & Humphrey, 2006). Participation by employees in the planning process may lead to innovation, which might provide possibilities and foster recognition within the organization (Zivkovic et al., 2009). According to their merits, managers provide subordinates the chance to participate in decision-making (Witte, 1980; Sagie & Aycon, 2003) in order to boost productivity and staff morale (Chang & Lorenzi, 1983). This gives workers the chance to exercise their brains, which will result in better judgments for the company (Williamson, 2008). According to Chang and Lorenzi (1983), employee engagement increases confidence and a sense of control. It lessens the resources needed to supervise employees, which lowers costs (Arthur, 1994; Spreitzes & Mishra, 1999). Hence, employee participation will improve employee wellbeing, which will lead to workforce sustainability.

Employee Development

Workplace democratic practices also emphasize employee development and learning, recognizing the importance of continuous growth and improvement. This can be achieved by providing opportunities for skill development, training, mentoring, coaching, and feedback to enhance employees' capabilities and enable them to contribute effectively to the organization. Employee development and learning can also involve creating a culture that values innovation, creativity, and learning from failures (Noe, 2010). The use of human resources to quantitatively change man's physical and biological surroundings for his advantage is what Ezeuwa (2009) defines as development. Another way to think about development is the influx of novel concepts that change the way society is organized and how people interact with one another. Development, according to Daniel (2003), is a means of quickening the advancement of both employees and the company so that competent people may occupy higher-level roles that are available within their expertise. According to Iwuoha (2009), development is primarily concerned with improving human connections. Staff development is becoming an increasingly essential and important need for businesses in the current corporate environment (Abdul Hameed 2011). According to Khawaja and Nadeem (2013), firms need to invest in continuous staff development if they want to retain employees and make sure the business succeeds. A community's or organization's ability to achieve and sustain a new planned state that benefits all participants is what Garavan et al. (1995) define as development. Worker market value, earning potential, and employment security are all enhanced and enabled by employee development, according to Obisi (2011). Development is the process by which new knowledge or abilities are acquired for one's own benefit. Organizations give their employees development programs to help them become more capable employees.

Fairness

Workplace democratic practices emphasize fairness, where employees are treated fairly in terms of rewards, recognition, and consequences. This can be achieved through clear expectations, performance evaluations, and fair policies and procedures for performance management, rewards, and recognition. Fairness also involves addressing grievances and conflicts in a transparent and unbiased manner (Greenberg, 1990). Fairness in the workplace is an important factor that can significantly impact employee performance. When employees perceive fairness in the allocation of resources, opportunities, and treatment, they are more likely to be motivated, engaged, and perform at higher levels.

According to a Colquitt et al. (2001) research, employee job satisfaction and performance were positively connected with views of distributive fairness. The fairness of the methods used in decision-making processes is known as procedural justice. According to research by Cropanzano et al. (2007), employee performance and procedural fairness were significantly positively correlated. The fairness of interpersonal interactions and communication throughout the decision-making process is known as interactional justice. Interactional justice has been shown to have a favorable impact on work performance and organizational civic behavior by Bies and Moag (1986). According to a 1999 research by Ambrose and Kulik, work performance was predicted by job satisfaction, which was highly correlated with views of fairness. These studies provide empirical proof that job satisfaction and employee performance are favorably correlated with workplace justice, and that these factors ultimately contribute to workforce sustainability. Thus, firms may promote workforce sustainability by ensuring justice in resource allocation, fair process implementation, and respectful and dignified treatment of workers. These actions will also improve employee motivation, engagement, and overall performance.

Concept of Workforce Sustainability

Workforce sustainability is a measurable factor that may help companies assess how well they're doing at creating inclusive, productive, and resilient jobs. Van Engen, Vinkenbunrg, and Dijkers (2012) stress that a focus on human sustainability "requires employers to take the present and future well-being and performance of their employees into account." Building on our discussion from earlier, we define a sustainable workforce as one whose members sustain their financial and mental health both at work and outside of it, in addition to having the positive energy, capacities, vitality, and resources necessary to meet current and future organizational performance requirements (Van Engen et al., 2012).

Employee Wellbeing

According to Diener (2000), wellbeing is critical to both individual and organizational success as well as mental and physical health. The significance of employee health and wellbeing is being more recognized by businesses. There is a growing desire to include wellness practices into the system, according to Hillier et al. (2005). In order to promote employee wellbeing and help them realize their full potential for the sake of the business and themselves, employers should provide a work atmosphere that is peaceful and joyful (CIPD, 2007). According to Oswald et al. (2014), enhancing well-being therefore has the critical capacity to motivate staff to perform diligently and strategically.

The influence of employee well-being (EWB) is also evident since individuals with higher EWB scores are more likely to adopt health-promoting attitudes and practices (Grant et al., 2009). Serxner et al. (2001) observed that participants in wellness programs had a lower absence ratio than those who did not participate. Wellness is a person's degree of wellbeing that leads to a greater quality of life, according to Corbin et al. (2002). Comprehensive study by Parks and Steelman (2008) indicates that workers who engage in corporate wellness programs report reduced stress, reduced absenteeism, increased job satisfaction, and increased productivity levels. Currie (2001) defined employee well-being as the combination of an employee's physical and mental health and their present degree of enjoyment. Implementing the EWB program in organizations aims to assist personal development, increase knowledge of wellness-related problems, and foster a productive and healthy work environment (Currie, 2001). The primary components of employee wellbeing (EWB) are emotional or effective experiences.

Empirical Review

In light of Lytton's (2012) research on the connection between workplace democracy and women's empowerment, employers ought to give female staff members the chance to participate in work-related conversations to make sure they understand the inner workings of their department and are capable of being empowered and performing well. They must also be dedicated to maintaining sex-based workplaces free from verbal and physical abuse. Additionally, while hiring, assigning, training, compensating, and promoting staff, the company should solely take into account their qualifications, performance, talents, and experience. In a recent study, based on demographic variables like gender, educational attainment, marital status, and work experience, Geçkil et al. (2016) investigated the relationship between physicians' and nurses' perceptions of organizational democracy (participation criticism, transparency, and accountability) and organizational psychological capital (optimism, resilience, hope, and self-efficacy).

Alonge and Olugbenga (2020) examine the connection between worker loyalty and organizational democracy in Nigeria's Rivers State's food and beverage industries. In this investigation, a cross-sectional survey was used since the variables were not within the researcher's control. 175 workers from the 15 registered food and beverage enterprises participated in this survey. Data were collected using a questionnaire, and the statistical method known as Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to analyze the information. In all, 150 surveys were successfully collected and utilized for the research, accounting for 85.71% of the total dispersed surveys. Thus, a significant relationship between organizational democratic traits and measures of employee commitment was found in the findings. Employee commitment to achieving organizational objectives is therefore seen to occur when firms implement organizational democracy. The paper suggests that in order to strengthen employee loyalty and weather tough times, the management of these organizations should advocate for a new organizational democracy strategy.

Gap in Literature

While there is existing research on workplace democratic practices and their impact on various aspects of organizational performance, there is a specific literature gap regarding their influence on workforce sustainability in manufacturing companies in Rivers State. Workforce sustainability encompasses factors such as employee well-being, job satisfaction, engagement, retention, and overall organizational resilience. The literature gap can be

summarized as the lack of comprehensive studies or empirical evidence specifically focusing on the relationship between workplace democratic practices and workforce sustainability in manufacturing companies within the context of Rivers State. Thus, the present study tends to bridge this gap in the literature.

Methodology

The research utilized a cross-sectional research design, which is a descriptive approach focused on survey research. The purpose of employing a cross-sectional research design is to collect and analyze data during a specific time period in order to generate conclusions and findings.

Population of the Study: The study included a total of 250 participants from 12 manufacturing companies located in Rivers State as the population of the study. Table 1 provided the detailed population information for the study.

Table 1: Population of the Study

S/N	Manufacturing Firms	Respondents
1	Eneral Agro Ind. Limited	45
2	Dangote Group of Companies Nig. Plc,	208
3	First Aluminum Co. Nig Ltd.	17
4	Triumph Drinks Nig. Ltd	19
5	Madona paints	116
6	Nigeria Bottling Co. Plc	140
7	Eastern Bulkcem Co. Ltd	85
Total		450

Source: Research Survey Report (2023).

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The statistical process of selecting a subset, or sample, from an interest population in order to observe and draw conclusions about that population, is known as sampling. The sample strategy developed by Taro Yamane (Yamane, 1967) was used in the investigation. This method helps in selecting 212 responses as the sample size from a large population of 450. Additionally, the approach described by Bowley (1964) was used to ensure that the questionnaire was distributed appropriately.

Methods of Data Collection and Instrumentation

This study employed quantitative research methods, which involved the statistical analysis of data obtained through questionnaires. The questionnaires used standardized scales or tests to numerically express the responses (Risjord et al., 2001). A total of 212 questionnaires were directly administered to respondents. The use of questionnaires for data collection proved advantageous as it allowed respondents sufficient time to carefully consider the questions before providing their responses.

Nature and Sources of Data: The primary data for this study were collected directly from the respondents, whereas the secondary data were gathered from sources such as management literature and materials from other relevant fields of study.

Operational Measurement of Variables

In this study, the predictor variable is workplace democratic practices, which encompass dimensions such as diversity, inclusivity, and open communication. The criterion variable is workforce sustainability, which is measured through indicators such as work-life balance and employee wellbeing. All variables were assessed using a modified Likert 4-point scale, ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree. Specifically, a score of 4 points was assigned to strongly agree, 3 points to agree, 2 points to disagree, and 1 point to strongly disagree.

Reliability of the Instrument: To ensure the reliability of the instruments used in the study, the Cronbach Alpha reliability test was employed. The benchmark for accepting the reliability of the instruments was set at a score of 0.7 or above, as established by Cronbach (1951). The reliability test was conducted using SPSS version 23.0. the following results were obtained: employee participation = 0.775, n = 4; employee development = 0.886, n = 4; fairness = 0.880, n = 3; employee wellbeing = 0.789, n = 4. This shows that the reliability of the instruments was achieved.

Data Analysis

Data analysis involves using statistical tools to examine and interpret data in order to generate findings. In this section, the collected quantitative data were analyzed using structural equation modeling, which included the use of path diagrams to illustrate the relationship between workplace democratic practices and workforce sustainability. The results of the analysis were interpreted and discussed in order to provide answers to the research questions and present the findings of the study.

Questionnaire Distribution and Retrieval Analysis

The researcher recorded and presented the information regarding the usable and unused copies of the questionnaire in tables. Table 2 displays the analysis of the distributed questionnaires and the corresponding percentage of retrieved copies that were included in the data analysis.

Table 2: Analysis of Questionnaire

S/N	Manufacturing Firms	Copies of questionnaire distributed	Copies of questionnaire retrieved	Abandoned Copies
1.	Eneral Agro Ind. Limited	21	21	-
2.	Dangote Group of Companies Nig Plc,	66	63	3
3.	First Aluminum Co. Nig Ltd.	8	8	-
4	Triumph Drinks Nig. Ltd	9	9	-
5	Madona paints	13	13	-
6	Nigeria Bottling Co. Plc	55	54	1
7	Eastern Bulkcem Co. Ltd	40	40	-
Total		212 (100%)	208 (98.1%)	4 (1.9%)

Source: Research data, (2023).

According to the findings presented in Table 2, a total of 212 (100%) questionnaires were distributed among the seven (7) manufacturing firms. Out of these, 208 (98.1%) were considered useful and included in the data analysis, while 4 (1.9%) questionnaires were abandoned or not completed. These results indicate a significant participation from the respondents, reflecting a successful administration of the questionnaires for data collection.

Table 3: Analysis of mean and standard deviation of Items on Technology Development

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Employee participation	3.2143	1.13389	208
Employee development	3.1429	1.60357	208
Fairness	3.2057	1.43649	208
Employee wellbeing	4.0357	1.34666	208

Source: SPSS Analysis Output (2023)

Based on the aforementioned findings, it is clear that all the items surpass the criterion mean of 3.5. As a result, the study acknowledges the significance of digital marketing strategies in ensuring customer retention.

Test of Hypotheses

The three statements of null hypotheses were tested in this section: this was done to ascertain relationship between employee participation and employee wellbeing of manufacturing companies in Rives State. To determine the relationship between employee development and employee wellbeing of manufacturing companies in Rives State. To examine the relationship between fairness and employee wellbeing of manufacturing companies in Rives State. Structural Equation model was used in the analyses with the help of Amos version of SPSS. The Output path diagram in figure 2 shows relationship between employee participation and employee wellbeing; employee development and employee wellbeing and the relationship between fairness and employee wellbeing of manufacturing companies in Rives State

Structural Equation Model using Amos Output path Diagram.

Figure 1. Structural Equation model showing Amos Output path Diagram.
 Source: Desk Research output Amos Output path Diagram

Interpretation of Result of the Tested Hypotheses

The study examined the relationship between workplace democratic practice and workforce sustainability. The relationship between employee participation and employee wellbeing was positive and significant (EP → EW, $\beta = 0.90$, $PV < 0.05$ level of significance) supporting H1. The relationship between employee development and employee wellbeing was positive and significant (ED → EW, $\beta = 0.61$, $PV < 0.05$) supporting H2. The relationship between fairness and employee wellbeing was positive and significant (F → EW, $\beta = 0.97$; $PV < 0.05$) supporting H3. Model and fit indices and hypotheses results are presented in table 1. In all, the square multiple correlation was **0.92** for employee wellbeing, this shows that 92% variance in employee wellbeing is counted by employee participation, employee development and fairness which are components of workplace democratic practices.

Findings

H_{A1}: There is a positive and significant relationship between employee participation and employee wellbeing of manufacturing companies in Rives State.

H_{A2}: There is a positive and significant relationship between employee development and employee wellbeing of manufacturing companies in Rives State.

H_{A3}: There is a positive and significant relationship between fairness and employee wellbeing of manufacturing companies in Rives State.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study were discussed as follows:

Positive and Significant relationship between employee participation and employee wellbeing.

Employee participation and employee well-being are interconnected aspects within the workplace. When employees are actively engaged and involved in decision-making processes, it can have a positive impact on their well-being. Studies have found that employee participation enhances a sense of autonomy and control, which contributes to improved well-being. Research by Bakker et al. (2014) revealed that employees who have a higher degree of control over their work experience lower levels of burnout and higher levels of job satisfaction. By involving employees in decision-making, organizations empower them to have a say in matters that affect their work, resulting in a sense of control and increased well-being.

Positive and significant relationship between employee development and employee wellbeing

Employee development and employee well-being are closely interconnected in the workplace. When employees are provided with opportunities for development and growth, it positively impacts their overall well-being, leading to increased job satisfaction, motivation, and productivity. This, in turn, benefits both the employees and the organization as a whole. Several studies and research papers have explored this relationship, providing insights and evidence to support the connection between employee development and well-being. A study by DeRue, et al. (2012) found that employees who participated in development activities reported higher levels of job satisfaction. This satisfaction stems from the sense of personal growth and achievement that comes with acquiring new skills and knowledge. When employees have access to development opportunities, it enhances their motivation and engagement at work. A meta-analysis conducted by Colquitt et al. (2000) revealed that training and development programs have a positive impact on employee motivation and performance.

Positive and significant relationship between fairness and employee wellbeing

The relationship between fairness and employee well-being is crucial in the workplace. When employees perceive fairness in organizational practices, policies, and interpersonal interactions, it positively influences their well-being, leading to greater job satisfaction, commitment, and overall psychological health. Several studies and research papers have examined this relationship, providing evidence to support the connection between fairness and employee well-being. Fairness has a significant impact on job satisfaction and organizational commitment, which are essential components of employee well-being. A study by Colquitt et al. (2001) demonstrated that perceived organizational justice, which includes distributive, procedural, and interactional fairness, is positively related to job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Fairness in the workplace contributes to employees' psychological well-being. Research by Cropanzano et al. (2001) demonstrated that perceived fairness positively influences employees' affective well-being, reducing negative emotions such as anxiety and depression.

Conclusion

Based on the findings the study conclude that employee participation in the workplace is crucial for fostering employee wellbeing which helps promote workplace sustainability in manufacturing companies in Rives State. Employee development through training programs will improve employee wellbeing which will enhance workforce sustainability of manufacturing companies in Rives State. Making clear expectations, performance evaluations, fair policies, procedures, rewards, and recognition will improve employee wellbeing of manufacturing companies in Rives State.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion, the following recommendations were made:

1. Management should involve employees in decision-making processes, seeking their input and feedback, and valuing their contributions to the organization as this will improve employee wellbeing which in turn enhances workforce sustainability of manufacturing companies in Rives State.
2. Management should provide opportunities for skill development, training, mentoring, coaching, and feedback to enhance employee wellbeing as this will lead to workforce sustainability of manufacturing companies in Rives State.
3. Management should provide clear expectations, performance evaluations, and fair policies and procedures, rewards, and recognition to improve employee wellbeing which will lead to workforce sustainability of manufacturing companies in Rives State.

Contribution to Knowledge

The workplace democratic practices and workforce sustainability of manufacturing companies in Rivers State contribute to the knowledge in several ways. By studying the democratic practices in manufacturing companies, researchers can contribute to the understanding of how democratic principles can be applied within an organizational context. This research shed light on the benefits and challenges of incorporating democratic practices in the workplace, such as employee participation, employee development and fairness.

Research on workplace democratic practices in manufacturing companies can contribute to knowledge by identifying strategies and practices that foster workforce sustainability. This knowledge can help manufacturing companies in Rivers State and beyond to develop sustainable workforce management strategies.

The study of workplace democratic practices can contribute to knowledge by examining their impact on workforce sustainability and employee well-being. Democratic practices, such as employee involvement in decision-making, can empower employees and increase their sense of ownership and satisfaction with their work. Understanding the factors that contribute to employee well-being can inform policies and practices that promote a healthy and productive work environment.

Thus, the study of workplace democratic practices and workforce sustainability in manufacturing companies in Rivers State contributes to knowledge by enhancing our understanding of the role of democracy in the workplace, promoting employee well-being and job satisfaction, identifying barriers and facilitators, and informing policy and practice.

Area for Further Research

While research on workplace democratic practices and workforce sustainability in manufacturing companies in Rivers State is valuable, there are several areas that can be explored further. Further research can focus on assessing the long-term impact of workplace democratic practices on organizational performance and sustainability. This can involve studying manufacturing companies in Rivers State over an extended period to examine how democratic practices contribute to their competitiveness, productivity, and overall success.

Future research can delve deeper into understanding the perspectives and experiences of employees in manufacturing companies regarding workplace democracy. This can involve qualitative research methods such as interviews or focus groups to gain insights into how employees perceive and engage with democratic practices, their satisfaction levels, and the factors that influence their participation.

Conducting comparative studies between manufacturing companies in Rivers State and those in other regions or countries can provide valuable insights into the contextual factors that influence the adoption and effectiveness of workplace democratic practices. Comparisons can be made with companies operating in different socio-cultural, economic, and regulatory environments to identify best practices and potential challenges. Research can explore the role of organizational culture and leadership in fostering workplace democratic practices and workforce sustainability. Investigating how leadership styles, organizational values, and cultural norms influence the adoption and implementation of democratic practices can provide a more comprehensive understanding of the dynamics involved.

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